

FOREST4EU partner: BOSCAT

OG: Calor Rural

OG's country: Spain

Type of Innovation: Social Innovation

Social network of sustainable forest use for the production of biomass for thermal purposes

Introduction

The lack of demand in the rural area of forest biomass for thermal purposes is a brake on the implementation of viable models of collective management of this resource. On the other hand, there are masses of trees with little commercial interest, currently unused, which increase the risk of fires and forest pests. It is necessary, therefore, to plan a collective management of forest masses and endogenous use of the resource that contributes to the circular economy that the rural environment requires, contributes to the creation of employment and resources, reduces GHG emissions to the atmosphere and minimizes fire risks and forest pests. It is essential that both administrations and the general public perceive the economic, social and environmental benefits of sustainable collective management of forest biomass. Creation of a social network for the use of forest biomass for thermal purposes, generating employment and resources, improving its management, contributing to the energy transition and reducing GHG emissions. Implement biomass exploitation networks based on the ownership of the masses, their management, optimizing collective production processes, and setting the business model. Design and implement the model of intervention in masses and forest remains of low commercial interest that minimize the risk of fires and proliferation of forest pests. Promote the use of biomass, in public buildings and local populations, and disseminate the resource as a source of renewable energy, reinforcing the role of the rural environment in the energy transition.

Lessons learned

The sustainable and viable use of forest biomass presents environmental, economic and social advantages in the territories. Environmental - Contribution to the 5C focal area and objectives 1 and 3 of EPI-AGRI: - Reduces the risk of forest fires due to the management of trees, eliminating excess fuel in the forest; - Reduce the emission of CO₂ into the atmosphere by replacing fossil fuel emissions; - It improves the stability of the forest masses through the application of viable intermediate silvicultural treatments; - 100 % renewable energy. Economic - Contribution to the 5C focal area and objectives 1 and 3 of EPI-AGRI: - Competitive discounts compared to other sources of energy (diesel, natural gas, etc.); - Encourages local economic activity; - Decreased external energy dependence, which favours the trade balance. Social - Contribution to the 5C focal area and to EPIAGRI objective 3: - New jobs for the creation of jobs in the rural environment (In the mountains with the creation of forestry teams, equipment, transport, logistics and distribution and in

points of consumption (machinery, installations, maintenance, boiler changes). Contribution to the circular economy - On the other hand, the proposed use, based on collective and grouped interests, as well as the use of the resource, fundamentally endogenous, enhances the circular economy by using this resource, closing the cycle of its life cycle. The creation of jobs in the rural area also contributes to generate economy in the territory where the resource is located.

Young people and women - The depopulation of rural areas is taking place, fundamentally, due to the lack of job opportunities for young people and women of the territory. The creation of new employment opportunities and new opportunities for entrepreneurship generated by the project will provide a better viability to the whole of the territories.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

[Grupo Operativo Calor Rural | Teder](#)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ohi5nZyFW6o&t=13s>

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